

QUALITY CONTROL OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC LONG TUBULAR MEMBERS

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SUMMARY: This paper presents the results of an experimental analysis on the mechanical properties of glass-fibre reinforced plastic (GRP) tubular conical columns widely used as cable supports by telephone and electric companies.

The aim of the study is mainly a quality control for the assessment of the characteristic values of the Young's modulus and the tensile strength of the material to be performed on specimens manufactured by different firms. Tensile tests have been carried out on specimens cut from the columns accordingly UNIPLAST EN-61 and ASTM D638-72. Usually, recommendations for bending tests (UNIPLAST EN-63 and ASTM D790-71) consider the possibility of evaluating the Young modulus of the material by testing small size specimens (of the same kind of the tensile specimens). Due to the large curvature of the tubes considered in this study, whose diameter is variable between 150 mm and 250 mm, the "slices" cut from the tubes for obtaining the specimens are not plane. A testing procedure was then identified, to perform four points bending tests on large size specimens (2 meters long) cut from the central portion of the tubes. Furthermore, compression tests have been performed on stubs.

The experimental data obtained from the 3 different types of testing and their statistics are compared and discussed.

KEYWORDS: long tubular members, mechanical behaviour, tensile Young's modulus of elasticity, tensile strength, bending modulus of elasticity

INTRODUCTION

Glass-fibre reinforced plastic columns are being extensively used for supporting light weights such as cables, lamps or antennas. They have many advantages over conventional materials (like wood, steel or concrete) such as light weight and high corrosion resistance and the mass production (as well as the technical improvements achieved in the last two decades) make composite materials convenient with respect to conventional ones from an economical point of view. Since 1984 GRP poles have been used in Italy to support overhead lines; many shapes and geometries are available, depending on the producer and on the application; usually, however, these poles were no more than 8 meters long. In 1990 a longer pole, 9 meters long, was adopted by a Company for sustaining overhead lines in street crossing. This occasion originated a co-operation between the Company and the Structural Engineering Department of Politecnico di Milano, with the aim of performing:

- 1) a quality control of the mechanical properties of the poles, manufactured by various firms all over the national territory;
- 2) a reliability analysis of the products delivered by the various manufacturers.

In the study, attention was concentrated on poles having an hollow truncated conical shape, 9 meters long; the maximum external diameter is equal to 250 mm and the minimum external diameter at the top section is equal to 115 mm. The nominal wall thickness is equal to 7.0 mm. All poles possess a perfectly smooth external surface and thus qualify at the 1st level of ASTM 2563-70 rules. Furthermore, the external surface is overlaid with a special not woven fabric, which guarantees protection against UV rays and environmental chemical attacks.

As the production procedures of these poles, which are centrifuged, are such that the glass fibre content (and consequently the mechanical properties of the material) vary along the longitudinal axis of the member, for each pole 5 portions were identified along the longitudinal axis (Fig. 1). From 4 portions compression and tensile specimens were obtained while from the intermediate portion a 2 m long specimen was obtained to be submitted to bending tests.

Usually, recommendations for bending tests - e.g. EN-63, ASTM D790-71 - consider the possibility of evaluating the Young modulus of the material by testing small size specimens (of the same kind of the tensile specimens) "sliced" from the member. Due to the large curvature of the tubes under evaluation, whose diameter is variable between 150 mm and 250 mm, the "slices" cut from the tubes, for obtaining the specimens are not plane. A testing procedure was then identified, to perform four points bending tests on 2 meters long specimens cut from the central portion of the columns.

Specimens cut from the 9 meters long pole were collected from six different producers; each firm provided 5 poles; for each pole provided one 2.0 m long specimen for bending test, 4 stubs for compression test and a total of 100 specimens for tensile test. A second phase of this study dealt with the axial load carrying capacity of these members. Full scale tests were carried out on 9 m long poles to analyse the behaviour of these members under working conditions. Experimental buckling tests were carried out on full scale tubes to analyse the working behaviour of the pole (Ref. /1/). The results of the first phase are herein presented and discussed. Concluding remarks complete the paper.

Fig. 1: Specimen outcoming zones

WORKING CONDITIONS OF THE MEMBERS AND MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS

Working conditions and Material

A particular application of tubular conical columns is their use as cable support by telephone and electric companies. With regard to this application the buckling problem is mainly connected to the corner poles of the lines which are guyed in order to reduce lateral deflections due to the transversal component of the cable tension. Hence, these members are subjected to compression and bending; the amplitude of the axial load depends on the transversal force and the guy inclination. The poles are usually driven into the ground for a length of 1.3 ± 0.2 m, and can be considered as cantilevered, with a 7.7 ± 0.2 m free length. Concerning to these working conditions, the companies adopting GRP poles defined technical recommendations about mechanical and geometrical properties, that should be provided by the different manufacturers. The leading requirements were related to the mean thickness (equal to 7 mm), the tensile strength (greater than 160 MPa) and the modulus of elasticity (greater than 20000 MPa).

Furthermore, all poles must guarantee protection against UV and chemical attacks.

All the poles were made by centrifugal casting, a production technique for fabricating cylindrical and conical shapes in which glass-fibre mats and roving are positioned inside a hollow mandrel designed to be heated and rotated as resin is cured. The internal side of the mandrel reproduces the external shape of the product. By controlling step by step the angular velocity - slow rotational velocity during the resin filling and a faster velocity during the curing - and the resin viscosity - mainly operating on the mandrel temperature -, it is possible to get a well impregnated fabric with an almost constant thickness; the poles tested, had a thickness included between 6.4 and 7.1 millimetres.

The poles were all produced with unsaturated (thermosetting) polyester resins, with E-glass fibres and fabrics.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Defining the mechanical properties of the material in the case of truncated conical tubes is not a conventional problem since:

- the specimens cut from the manufacture do not result plane but they have concavity, which could produce difficulties during the test; as a matter of fact, in tensile tests, the clamps can carve the specimen that can break. Furthermore, in conventional bending test the specimen convexity makes hard the correct load application and the specimen arc behaviour in transversal direction causes bias in the results.
- glass-fibre reinforced plastic, as all the fibre-reinforced materials, towers for its anisotropic behaviour, and it is strongly influenced from profile working like the preparation of the specimen.

Since the aim was to get a reliable value of mechanical properties of the material, it was decided to consider specimens with dimension not influenced from tool working by deriving them from longitudinal and transversal cutting, at different levels of the pole axis.

The specimens were manufactured in six batches from six different producers. Each manufacturer provided 5 poles. Each pole was cut in 5 sections. From the intermediate section, 2 meter long, a 4 point bending test specimen was obtained. From each of the two upper and the two lower sections one compression test specimen having a slenderness ratio $\lambda = 6$ according to the UNIPLAST 4279 specifications (ASTM D695-69 prescribes $\lambda = 11\div 15$) and five 400 mm long tensile test specimens were obtained.

In total each manufacturer provided:

- five 2 meter long flexural specimens
- one hundred 400 mm long tensile specimens
- twenty $\lambda = 6$ compression stubs.

Furthermore, since the aim of the study was to get information about the product quality from a mechanical performance point of view, an evaluation of physical specimen parameters was carried out to determinate glassfibre volumetric content and specimen thickness. By tensile strength and Young's modulus, the effective rigidity was calculated and correlated to the glass percentage and specimen thickness.

Tensile Tests

Tensile tests were carried out on specimens 25 mm wide and 400 mm long, to get a mid-part length equal to 200 mm where the stress is not influenced by the external clamps and by the tool working of the ends; in fact, to prepare the specimen, both ends were worked by some resin cured and levelled to make the surfaces complanate with the clamps of the testing machine (EN-61). Furthermore, to improve the adherence between the specimen and the clamps, some carborundum dust was applied on the resin reinforcements at the ends.

The specimen is qualitatively illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Tensile specimen (qualitative)

Test were carried out by means of a Schenk universal testing machine having a 2000 kN total capacity.

The load applied on the specimen was measured by a dynamometer while the elongation was got by LVDT, with reference length equal to 100 mm, directly applied on the specimen.

By this way it was possible to measure the exact strain of the specimen and to keep out any spurious component due to the axial strain of the testing machine and to the sliding of the specimen between the clamps.

Compression Tests

The measured compression strength of composites is sensitive to the specimen configuration and the fixture used for loading. Compression tests have been performed on 4 stubs per column. The slenderness λ for stubs has been evaluated as the ratio between specimen length and midspan radius of inertia. All stubs have the same slenderness equal to 6, according to the Italian rule UNIPLAST 4279. The slenderness has been adopted to define the specimen length, as a function of its transversal dimensions. The experimental analysis was carried out on stubs obtained from cutting the poles at different levels as it is illustrated in Fig. 1. The test stubs were cut to size with a high degree of accuracy using a diamond tip saw, and, later on, levelled with a precision within 0.1 mm. The analysis was performed by displacement controlled centred compression tests using a numeric control testing machine MTS with maximum load equal to 2300 kN. This machine is adequately stiff and rigid enough to reduce any possible secondary effect such as the machine/test-rig interaction. The stub displacements were measured by four LVDTs installed between the testing machine plates in opposite diametral positions. Before leading the specimens to collapse, compression loading cycles were applied to each specimen to evaluate its behaviour and testing repeatability under different load levels.

Bending Tests

As the aim of the investigation was to get information about the in service behaviour of the poles and in order to avoid the procedural problems involved with the large curvature of the members, resulting in a concavity of the specimens usually prescribed by recommendations for bending tests, it was decided to disregard recommended testing procedures such as those proposed in UNIPLAST EN-63 and, in the case of bending tests, to identify an ad hoc testing procedure, operating on large size specimens (2.0 meters long) cut from the central portion of the pole. The cutting position along the pole axis was decided according to the following items:

- the mats are usually positioned not uniformly along the pole axis and, because of the truncated cone shape, the most of them are concentrated in the lower part of the pole where the diameter is maximum. Only few mats go up to the end of the pole while all the others stop at different elevations; similar distributions are adopted by various manufacturers although the length of each mat is different for every producer. As a matter of fact, in order to get information about the average behaviour, it was decided to analyse a part of the pole where mats are distributed on average; the mechanical properties, in fact, are related to the glass fibre content and higher values could be obtained by testing the pole lower part which usually represents the most stressed section if the member is a cantilever.
- the poles are produced by different firms and consequently their dimensions are different for the various manufactures.

In order to maintain the same testing configuration for all specimens, it was asked to the manufacturers to provide - from the intermediate part of the pole - a 2.0 m long specimen, having a given diameter at two cross section spaced 1800 mm. In fact, the specimens were supported at the end by two wooden saddles of 100 mm-width. The saddles were shaped to keep the longitudinal axis of the specimen horizontal and to surround a semicircular half of

the tube. This support shape reduces deformability and section ovalization under the applied loads and prevents out-of-plane displacements of the specimen.

Furthermore, rubber pads (Teflon) were placed on both supports in order to reduce friction between the saddle and the specimen and to avoid local failures; of course, this testing configuration caused the specimen to have well defined transversal dimensions.

An hydraulic jack was used to apply the load that was distributed to two loading points located at the third points of the stub using a steel beam and two additional wooden saddles. The magnitude of the total applied load (i.e., two times the load at each load point on the log) was monitored by a load cell placed in series with the hydraulic jack.

Vertical displacements were measured using 5 linear LVDT. The deflections were measured at the specimen midspan, at the two load points and at 5/12 and 7/12 of the span.

Each specimen was loaded in a series of short term loading/unloading cycles to verify the mechanical behaviour and its reproducibility under different load levels.

The target load was fixed equal to 100 kN although some stubs collapsed before the target load was reached.

RESULTS

The normal model was used to calculate the characteristic values B . They have been calculated in terms of the sample mean \bar{X} and standard deviation S using the formula:

$$B = \bar{X} - kS \quad (1)$$

where k is a coefficient connected to the risk formulation $1-\alpha$ and to the confidence level. A 95% probability of survival was assumed, connected to 95% confidence level, in order to define the characteristic values of the various properties.

To get information about production quality by mechanical material properties, all the data obtained were computed following the described procedure.

The computing was mainly aimed to identify the elastic modulus mean value E_m , the root-mean-square deviation S and the Young's modulus characteristic value E_b by the application of :

$$E_b = E_m - kS \quad (2)$$

Tensile Young's Modulus

Because of the small specimen width equal to 25 mm, the area A was measured by concavity neglecting.

The initial tangent Young's modulus E_T was computed by the following formula:

$$E_T = \frac{l_0 \cdot R \cdot \Delta F_1}{A \cdot \Delta Z_1} \quad (3)$$

where $l_0 = 100$ mm is the LVDT reference length, R is the magnification typical transformer coefficient, ΔF_1 is the load variation and ΔZ_1 is the apparent elongation variation connected to ΔF_1 .

The test results showed an increasing of the Young's modulus with strain. The tensile secant modulus of elasticity E_S was evaluated according to UNI-EN61, basing on Eqn. 3 with ΔZ_1 corresponding to a 0.5% apparent elongation percentage.

Considering the target values, testing phase was carried out as shown in Table 1 where are illustrated the values got for the poles manufactured by the six different firms herein called A, B, C, D, E and F.

Table 1: Tensile Young's modulus statistics

FIRM	E_{mT} (MPa)	E_{bT} (MPa)	S (MPa)
A	26495	21175	2700
B	23384	20383	1436
C	25230	22640	1282
D	22586	20241	782
E	22616	16817	2416
F	22944	19669	1621

A global analysis of results has been carried out as shown in Fig. 3 where the Young's modulus distribution is illustrated; it was derived considering the whole batch. The figure shows that the specimens that don't touch the target value are less than 3.5% of the total. Despite this fact, because of the standard deviation high value - $S = 2598$ MPa - the resulting characteristic value of the tensile Young modulus is 19733 MPa, a little lower than the target required. Then, a statistical analysis has been performed considering the zone where the specimen was got from; all the specimens were cut from 4 different pole levels as shown in Fig. 1. Table 2 illustrates the results got for each level; it shows how the Young's modulus increases moving from the top of the pole - level 1 - to its lower part - level 5 -. Level 5 shows lower values than level 4 ; it is due to a great result dispersion with 20 results above 26000 MPa. Neglecting them, the target values are got.

Table 2: Tensile Young's modulus statistics per level

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 4	Level 5
E_{mT} (MPa)	24064	24308	24456	23885
E_{bT} (MPa)	17569	19302	20581	20246
S (MPa)	3168	2515	1947	1793

The mean values are always greater than the target required; the characteristic values are greater than the target only for the fourth and the fifth levels. The values progress is mainly due to the high concentration of glass-fibre in the lowest part of the pole where there is the most stressed section in operative conditions. By this reason, it seemed acceptable to re-calculate the distribution of tensile elastic modulus values of Fig. 3 by ignoring specimens which belong to level 1.

The result is shown in Fig. 4: by re-analysing the new sample, a value of $E_{bT} = 21372$ MPa is obtained, satisfying the minimum required.

Fig. 3: Young's modulus distribution (all levels) Fig. 4: Young's modulus distribution (levels 2,4 & 5)

Tensile Strength

The ultimate tensile strength was evaluated for the four levels with the same procedure used for Young's Modulus computing; main results are shortly resumed in Table 3.

Table 3: Ultimate tensile strength statistics for each pile level

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 4	Level 5
f_{mT} (MPa)	281.8	292.6	301.3	311.1
f_{bT} (MPa)	183.5	199.7	183.6	193.6
S (MPa)	47.9	46.7	59.2	59.0

where f_{mT} and f_{bT} are respectively the mean value and the characteristic value for the ultimate tensile strength. The distribution is shown in Fig. 5. The correlation between tensile strength and glassfibre volumetric content is discussed in § 5.

Thickness

A statistical analysis of specimen thickness was performed during tensile tests.

About half of the total specimen sample has a thickness lower than the 7 mm required. The mean value is 7.15 mm but, being $S = 1.17$ mm, the characteristic value is 5.03 mm; in Fig. 6 the Young's modulus is correlated to the specimen thickness; a large scattering is evident. According to the "mixing rule" (Voigt model), the figure also shows that at increasing thickness corresponds a decreasing tensile modulus.

If E_{gf} and E_m are respectively the glassfibre and the matrix Young's modulus and α is the glassfibre volumetric content, the composite Young's modulus can be derived from the following formula:

$$E_t = \alpha E_{gf} + (1 - \alpha) E_m + E_{int} \quad (4)$$

where E_{int} means the effect of the different lateral strain due to the different Poisson's ratios of the two materials. In elastic field E_{int} is negligible. Being $E_{gf} \gg E_m$, if during manufacturing α value decreases - i.e. the resin volumetric content increases more than the glassfibre volumetric content - also the value of E_t decreases.

Furthermore, the ultimate tensile strength appeared to decrease with the increasing thickness; this fact confirms the need for caution in applying design allowables derived from small scale tests to large GRP structures.

Fig. 5: Tensile strength distribution

Fig. 6: E_T predicted by thickness

Compressive Modulus of Elasticity

The experimental analysis was carried out by MTS testing machine. This is able to provide a maximum load of 2300 kN. The high magnification drum recorder integral to the MTS machine was used to plot the load/end-shortening curves.

Cyclic loads were applied to each specimen to evaluate its behaviour and the repeatability under different load levels. After the checking and several loading and unloading tests, the specimen was then tested to failure.

Since the testing machine had a displacement controlled process, collapse of the panel was denoted as a sudden reduction in load.

The theoretical specimen shortening was estimated by numerical integration of the virtual work equation. The shortening was calculated as the mean of the two values measured by LVDT placed between the testing machine plates on opposite sides.

The secant modulus of elasticity was evaluated by numerical computing of the slope of the lines connecting in the stress and strain plane points corresponding to load increments equal to 10 kN.

By a statistical interpretation of the results, the mean value computed for different load levels was obtained. Furthermore, the standard deviation allowed interesting information about the linearity of the diagram to be obtained. The characteristic value of the modulus of elasticity measured by compression tests resulted far from the minimum required. Mainly, the Young's modulus showed a decreasing behaviour with strain increasing. These values are illustrated in Table 4, where E_{mC} is the mean value while E_{bC} is the characteristic value.

Table 4: Compressive modulus of elasticity statistics

FIRM	E_{mC} (MPa)	E_{bC} (MPa)	S (MPa)
A	17011	12975	1345
B	20716	13532	2395
C	20093	12956	2379
D	20691	12389	2768
E	21333	16423	1637
F	20552	13865	2229

Bending Modulus of Elasticity

The load was applied within the elastic range and removed to allow the specimen to further settle.

After the checking and several loading and unloading tests, the specimen was then tested to failure. For all tests fibre breaking could be heard well before final failure. There was quite a significant variation in the way the failures occurred. In few cases it initiated on the supports due to the shear force. In bending there are displacement gradients also in the circumferential direction in addition to those gradients in the axial direction. The intralayers stresses associated with these displacement gradients, coupled with the brittle nature of the material, can be severe enough to cause material failure within these boundary regions. In most cases failure started at the loading saddles or in the mid span zone. The values computed are illustrated in Table 5, where E_{mB} is the mean value while E_{bB} is the basis value.

Table 5: Bending modulus of elasticity statistics

FIRM	E_{mB} (MPa)	E_{bB} (MPa)	S (MPa)
A	22762	19451	1850
B	20486	19550	529
C	20500	19406	618
D	21588	20318	572
E	22923	21572	764
F	19765	18825	531

With bending, in addition to the possibility of material failure on the compression and tension sides of the structure there is also the stability issues associated with the compression side of the truncated cone.

Chemical and Physical Parameters

Some other important parameters, such as glass percentage and specific weight, have been investigated during testing phase.

A polymer analysis was accomplished with x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). This technique provides a total element analysis and the chemical bonding information.

By XPS, the matrix composition was determined for the whole batch as a mixture of polystyrene with unsaturated polyester. Mainly, specific weight SW and glassfibre volumetric content α were measured providing a mean specific weight equal to 1.49 and the following values for α : $\alpha_m = 72.9\%$, $\alpha_b = 61.1\%$ and $S = 3.9\%$. The glassfibre volumetric content distribution computed for a single batch is illustrated in Fig. 7; Fig. 8 shows for the same batch the correlation between E_t and the specimen glass percentage. By this analysis it was possible to get the correct α values and to verify once more the “mixing rule” accuracy.

Fig. 7: Glassfibre vol. content distribution

Fig. 8: E_T predicted by glassfibre vol. content

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Composite cylindrical and quasi-cylindrical structures, such as the examined ones, are known for their efficiency. The curvature effectively increases the stiffness of the structure, resulting in a more economical use of material.

From experimental analysis it is found that the compressive modulus of GRP decreases with strain whilst the tensile modulus increases. This can result in much lower stresses on the compression side of the specimen than on the tension side; although in bending tests failure often begins on the compression side because of geometric non-linear response.

The experimental investigation has shown a good agreement with the theoretical mixing rule, by which it is possible to predict the Young's tensile modulus vs. glassfibre volumetric content α (Fig. 8).

Furthermore, the correlation between tensile strength f_T and glassfibre volumetric content, illustrated in Fig. 9, confirms theoretical predictions; when α is lower than α_{\min} , material behaviour is governed by matrix deformation and is lower than matrix resistance; for $\alpha_{\min} < \alpha < \alpha_{\text{cr}}$ the GRP material resistance is controlled by fibre deformation but is lower than matrix resistance. Only for α greater than α_{cr} there is an effective matrix reinforcement by glassfibre so that α_{cr} is a minimum target that must be exceeded.

Fig. 9: f_T predicted by glassfibre volumetric content

Testing analyses showed that a wide experimental investigation is needed in order to design GRP structures; as a matter of fact, all testing phases confirm the need for caution in applying design allowables derived from small scale tests to large GRP structures.

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